

SparkSoft:

Building an AI toolkit to help farmers detect and manage crop pests, with BridgeAI internship support

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If you don't work in agriculture, you probably haven't heard of plant-parasitic nematodes. But if you do work in agriculture, you'll know that these microscopic worms can have a big – and costly – impact.

Plant-parasitic nematodes (PPN) are routinely associated with approximately 5-20% yield loss across agricultural crops, corresponding to an estimate around ~US\$175 billion worth of crop losses each year worldwide. When impacts on non-commercial crops in developing and under-developed regions are included, this figure is believed to rise to around US\$200 billion per year. The scale of the challenge is especially apparent in the UK potato sector. Analysis by the Agriculture and Horticulture Development Board (AHDB) and industry specialists at ADAS indicates that approximately 65% of land used for ware potato production in England and Wales is infested with potato cyst nematode (PCN). The resulting direct economic impact on the UK potato industry has been estimated at around £50 million per year. In Scotland, which produces around three-quarters of the UK's seed potatoes, the consequences are even more strategic. The Scottish PCN Working Group estimates that PCN infestation leads to an opportunity loss of approximately £5,000 per hectare, equivalent to around £25 million in annual losses to Scottish potato production. Without effective intervention, these losses are projected to increase to approximately £125 million by 2040.

Credit: adobestock

Recent UK Plant Health Centre analyses further underline the urgency of the problem. A PCN Scenario Planner release reports that PCN-infested land in Scotland is doubling roughly every seven years, while a 2025 follow-up briefing (published via the Aberdeen & Grampian Chamber of Commerce and drawing on research from The James Hutton Institute) estimates that around 41% of Scottish ware potato land is already affected by PCN. Reducing these losses through improved diagnostics, non-chemical control strategies, and precision, data-driven approaches would therefore deliver substantial benefits for growers, strengthen the resilience of food production systems, and support long-term food security, an industry challenge now being actively addressed by UK-based company [SparkSoft](#).

A well-established IT consultancy providing software engineering solutions for its customers, SparkSoft has developed a particular focus on precision agriculture. The SparkSoft team is creating an AI-driven platform that brings together image detection, predictive technology, and user-friendly interface to give growers practical and automated guidance on how to identify, quantify and forecast pests infections and emerging outbreak risks, enabling targeted interventions that significantly reduce unnecessary pesticide use and support more sustainable, data-led farming practices. To help push this project forward, SparkSoft founder Peng Yue joined Innovate UK's BridgeAI programme. Through BridgeAI, Peng was matched with an Independent Scientific Advisor, Professor Po Yang, and a technology-focused intern, computer science PhD student Zhipeng Yuan – both from the University of Sheffield.

Across a three-month placement, Zhipeng worked on two interlinked parts of SparkSoft's pest management platform, known as PPNAnalyzer, addressing a clear technical need. First, Zhipeng strengthened the data and computer vision modelling foundations underpinning the system, this included expanding and curating SparkSoft's training dataset to ~5,000+ labelled images across six common plant-parasitic nematode (PPN) species, standardising annotation formats, improving class balance, and introducing clearer dataset splits and versioning to support repeatable training and evaluation. These updates improved overall dataset reliability (e.g., reduced duplication and inconsistent labels) and made the data easier for engineers and collaborators to maintain and extend. Building on the improved data pipeline, Zhipeng optimised the detection workflow to increase robustness and accuracy, reaching a 96% mean average precision, providing a stronger technical baseline for deployment and ongoing improvement.

Alongside image-based detection, Zhipeng also developed a prototype for PPN distribution prediction, translating environmental and soil covariates into spatial risk estimates. Using a maximum entropy (MaxEnt) approach, he integrated available layers such as climate variables and soil properties to generate probability surfaces indicating where each nematode species is most likely to occur. This work demonstrated how the platform can move beyond “what is in this sample?” toward “where is the risk likely to increase next?”, supporting more proactive pest management and field planning.

“From SparkSoft’s perspective,” says Peng, “the internship has been highly valuable for us. It provided targeted technical support at an important stage of our development and helped us strengthen the foundations of our AI-driven precision agriculture platform. One of the clearest benefits was support in developing our pest quantification and predictive modelling capability has significantly expanded our opportunities to deliver more effective and forward-looking pest management solutions”.

Peng Yue,
Founder SparkSoft

“The intern also contributed to the development of a functional minimum viable product (MVP) of our user-facing AI assistant, this assistant is designed to help growers interpret complex pest-related information through natural language queries, for example, questions about pest species, infestation risk, or the influence of weather conditions.” Rather than relying on a single model, the system uses a multi-agent architecture, with dedicated components responsible for tasks such as identifying nematodes from images, predicting their likely spread, and searching relevant contextual documents. These components are integrated using a system known as retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) framework, enabling the assistant to ground its responses in verified data sources rather than producing generic outputs. “This tool has given us a real sense of how language model features could be integrated into our products and helped us understand where these tools could benefit our stakeholders in agriculture. Zhipeng’s clear academic documentation and experiment logs were also particularly valuable for us as a small company, as they improved visibility of research progress and supported more informed decisions around technical focus and resource allocation.”

Through the internship, Zhipeng strengthened his technical skills in areas such as multi-agent systems and the application of large language models – particularly in a business-focused context. This, he says, will be of great value for his longer-term career development, in which he aims to combine academic research with solving practical industry problems.

Po, who has a longstanding relationship with SparkSoft, played a key role in helping Zhipeng understand how academic AI models can work in industry settings. He adds: “The internship progressed very well, and Zhipeng quickly became an effective and proactive member of SparkSoft’s research and development team. He made a significant contribution by enhancing the company’s nematode recognition and analysis platform, integrating state-of-the-art AI techniques combining pattern recognition with rule-based reasoning. This has improved the functionality, transparency and auditability of SparkSoft’s platform. Zhipeng has also engaged effectively with external research partners in the sector such as ADAS and Fera, helping to align the technical work with real-world agricultural and regulatory requirements.”

As a direct outcome of Zhipeng’s work during the internship, SparkSoft secured a three-month Innovate UK Sovereign AI proof-of-concept award to further develop its platform. The Sovereign AI initiative aims to validate scalable AI technologies with the potential to make an impact in areas of strategic importance to the UK.

About Innovate UK BridgeAI

Innovate UK BridgeAI empowers UK businesses in high-growth sectors, driving productivity and economic growth through the adoption of Artificial Intelligence. We bridge the gap between developers and end-users, fostering user-driven AI technologies.

With a focus on ethics, transparency and data privacy, we aim to build trust and confidence in the development of AI solutions. Strengthening AI leadership, supporting workforces, and promoting responsible innovation, BridgeAI shapes a collaborative and AI-enabled future.

BridgeAI is an Innovate UK funded programme, delivered by a consortium including Innovate UK, Digital Catapult, The Alan Turing Institute, STFC Hartree and BSI.

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